

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT: ENVISIONING A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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Paper Received On: 12 March 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 28 March 2024

Published On: 01 April 2024

Abstract

Sustainable societies cater to the diverse needs of all the people in the society. Sustainable development is about addressing the intermingling issues that we encounter in societies today. In this context the role of women in ensuring a sustainable society needs to be focused on. Women's role based on traditional concepts of gender of carrying out domestic responsibilities, caring for the family, managing the household puts her in close contact with the environment. Women are more vulnerable to the impact of environmental challenges facing societies across the world. Addressing gender-based issues and finding ways to meet the challenges and empowerment of women can lead to more gains in building sustainable societies.

Key words: Sustainable development, Women empowerment, gender equality

Introduction:

Sustainable development provides a framework for building societies that balance the needs of people and the preservation of the environment and avoid focusing on one at the expense of the other. Sustainable societies cater to the diverse needs of all the people in the society. In this context the role of women in ensuring a sustainable society needs to be focused on. Women's role based on traditional ideas and norms of gender of that of the primary caregiver and basic responsibilities of managing the household puts her in close contact with the environment. In many communities across the world women carry out the domestic responsibilities of taking care of the family, providing for food and taking care of their daily needs, taking care of animals etc. that has significant environmental implications. It also seen that during natural calamities or disasters it is women that bear the brunt of the effects. The Rio Declaration at the UN

Conference on Environment and Development 1992 stated that ‘women have a vital role in environmental management and development. Their full participation is therefore essential to achieve sustainable development. It also recommended that governments should develop ways to ‘eliminate constitutional, legal, administrative, cultural, behavioural, social and economic obstacles to women’s full participation in sustainable development and in public life. As awareness increases as to how intertwined are environmental, economic and social issues it brings to the forefront the importance of gender equality and sustainable development. Achieving the objectives of sustainable living needs to invest in the development, inclusion, equality and safety of women. It is essential that efforts towards meeting the challenges of environmental degradation, climate change, need to have a women focused approach.

Women and environment:

Women are more likely than men to be affected by climate change. They are most vulnerable to the impact of environmental challenges facing societies across the world. An important area of concern identified by the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action at the Fourth World Conference on Women 1995 was women and the environment that laid out three objectives towards action on environment. It pertained to inclusion of women in all aspects of decision making, integrating their concerns and views in policies and programmes and designing assessment measures to evaluate the impact of development and environmental policies on women. ‘Environmental decision making – decisions we make for people and planet – need to be inclusive and involve all voices, including equal voices from women. The triple planetary crisis – of climate, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste – places a triple burden on women. According to UN Women, climate-related extreme events can lead to increased violence against women and girls. And we know that biodiversity loss places profound pressures on women and girls as land managers and resource users. And as food producers, women are frequently at greater risk through endocrine-disrupting chemicals in pesticides, or persistent organic pollutants (POPs).’ Inger Andersen, Executive Director, UN Environment Programme, on International Women’s Day 2021. Inclusion of women and utilising their knowledge and skills can play a critical part in ensuring that natural resources are utilised in an efficient and sustainable way.

Challenges:

Some of the gender-based challenges that needs to be addressed to promote sustainable development include the following-

- Daily living challenges: Across the world women face great challenges in their daily life activities for instances in many areas women travel great distances to get water. The

burden of fetching water falls on women and it is a task that involves great risk as they venture great distances and takes up a large part of their time and takes them away from activities such as education, income generating activities. Water management is a crucial part of their daily living responsibilities.

- Food Security

The stress on agriculture and other resources due to climate change, land and water degradation pose challenges for many communities and women are at an increased disadvantage. Women are involved in various areas of agricultural sector and are participants in the cultivation of crops and animal husbandry, yet cultural and social norms and customs prevent them from having access or owning resources. They are prevented from owning land or property, are restricted access to resources and this has a strong impact on the food security of women. They face higher risk of malnutrition and other health issues due to lack of appropriate food and nutrition.

- Health risks

Women face higher health risks due to lack of access to resources and nutrition requirements. Long hours of involvement in agricultural work, household responsibilities, reduced share in available food and nutrition due to cultural practices, pollution, pesticides, poverty, lack of access to basic healthcare services all leading to increased health risks for women. Poor maternal health care is another critical aspect of heightened risk to women's health. Women's health issues are not prioritised as they are not considered important on equal basis as men in the society. Lack of access to proper sanitation is also a significant concern in many societies. Availability of water, accessibility, security are pertinent challenges that women face with respect to sanitation.

- Education

Education is a key factor in empowering women and paving the way for gender equality in societies. Education enables individuals to develop their knowledge and skills, participate in the society, be aware of their rights and increased employment opportunities. Education can lead to more informed individuals and societies who can provide the impetus needed for achieving the objective of sustainable development. Though there have been steady improvement in the rate of women receiving educational opportunities yet due to social and cultural beliefs yet there are wide gaps in the enrolment of girls in education as compared to boys. Environmental challenges create stress on availability of resources leading to resources

being allotted to people who are viewed to be important in the society. In patrilineal societies women stand to be deprived of receiving an equal share in the resources.

Way Ahead:

Considering a gender- based approach is essential for advancing a sustainable future for all. Some of the measures that can aid in accomplishing this goal includes-

- Ensuring increased participation of women in all decision-making processes. Advancement of sustainable development can be strengthened with the involvement of women in decision making process. Gender equality, women empowerment are key factors in leading to accomplishing sustainable development.
- Access and availability of safe water resources, reforms in laws and policy making is needed to remove discrimination against women in ownership of land and property. Women need to be involved in the decision-making process with respect to the management of these resources.
- Creating health care systems that caters to the different health needs of women and men. The social and cultural aspects that propagates discriminatory practices towards women's health needs to be addressed.
- Providing educational opportunities, increasing accessibility, capacity building initiatives, more community engagements for shifting attitudes and beliefs towards gender equality is needed. Increased focus is required on providing quality education that integrates gender equality and empowerment of women.

Conclusion:

Sustainable development becomes more relevant and realistic when it weaves together the requirements of the social, economic and environmental elements. As the issues we face today are intermingled one arising from and affecting another we need to develop a holistic perspective in addressing these issues. Addressing gender discrimination, integrating women into decision making process and prioritizing women empowerment and equality are central to building a more sustainable society.

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